

Tu Mecum Es In Pectore Meo

You Are with Me, You are my Soul

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Veni ad me, da mihi basium
Come to me and kiss me
Da mi basia
Kiss me more
Da mi mille basiorum
Make it a thousand times more

Saltemus una
Let us dance together
Visne, mecum saltare
Would you dance with me?
Veni, saltare mecum
Come, dance with me.

Verba tua dulces sunt sicut mel
Your words are pure love like honey
Sicut lenes venti in facie mea spirantes morantur
Like the soft breeze breathing on my face
Cupio audire, mecumque manent
I long to hear them, and they rest in me.

Mellifluous, susurus, "vere te amo, mi dulcis facies."
Flowing like honey, whispering, "I honestly love you, my dear, your face is so sweet."
Te videre cupio
I long to see you.
In cordeo meo, mecum es.
In my heart, you are with me.

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